

On the Impact of the Coordinate Representation onto the Estimates in Least-Squares Adjustment

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Abstract In geodesy and metrology several coordinate representations are known. The most important representations are polar coordinates and Cartesian coordinates. The coordinate representations are rigorously convertible into each other. Such functional relations are well-known as the direct (first) and the inverse (second) geodetic problem. Instruments like e. g. total station, laser scanner, or laser tracker are polar measurement systems. It is common practise especially in surface analysis, e. g. deformation analysis of the VLBI main reflector, to initially convert the obtained polar coordinates into their Cartesian representations. Instead of the polar measurements, the converted Cartesian coordinates are introduced to the least-squares adjustment. In this investigation, the impact of the chosen coordinate representation onto the estimates is studied. It is shown that the adequate transformation of the functional model and the stochastic model of the least-squares adjustment is not sufficient to obtain identical estimates.

Keywords Paraboloid, Least-Squares Adjustment, Sequential Quadratic Programming, Surface Analysis, Cartesian Coordinates, Polar Coordinates, GeoMetre

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1 Introduction

In geodesy and metrology different coordinate representations are in use, like e. g. polar or Cartesian coordinates. These representations are rigorously convertible into each other, known as the direct (first) and the inverse (second) geodetic problem. In most metrology applications, one has to deal with two coordinate representations, i. e., the representation of the observation space and the representation of the parameter space. Whereas the first one is related to the raw observations obtained by the measurement instrument, the second one relates to the target coordinate system of the parameters to be estimated.

For instance, a total station used for reference point determination at VLBI radio telescopes is a polar measurement instrument (e. g. Lösler et al., 2013; Kallio et al., 2016). The polar observations spans the observation space. However, the estimated coordinates of the reference point are usually related to a Cartesian coordinate system. Obviously, the coordinate representation of the observation space differs from the coordinate representation of the parameter space.

A further example comes from surface analysis, e. g., measuring the main reflector of a VLBI radio telescope (e. g. Sarti et al., 2009; Holst et al., 2017). If a laser scanner is used, the observation space is spanned by a polar system, because the physical measurement principle of the instrument provides the slope distance, the azimuth angle, and the zenith angle of an observed position. The parameters to be estimated, e. g. the focal length and the position of the apex, are usually specified in a Cartesian coordinate system. Again, the representations of both spaces differ from each other.

Since rigorous conversions exist to interchange between coordinate representations, such conversions can

take place in the observation space but also in the parameter space. In several metrology applications, it is common practise to initially convert the obtained polar coordinates into their Cartesian representations (cf. Holst et al., 2012; Lösler et al., 2016). Thus, the polar representation of the observation space is converted to its Cartesian representation, including the coordinates of the observed positions as well as the related measurement uncertainties. The later one is usually converted by applying the propagation of uncertainty.

In a least-squares adjustment, the functional model connects the observation space and the parameter space. For that reason, the functional model has to be specified depending on the chosen coordinate representations of both spaces. The parameters to be estimated are derived by minimising the weighted squared observational residuals, and, thus, the objective function *may* depend on the chosen coordinate representation of the observations.

In this contribution, the impact of the chosen coordinate representation of the observation space onto the estimates is studied. The assumption whether the estimates remain unaffected by interchanging the coordinate representation is investigated, exemplified at the best-fit paraboloid. Moreover, the impact of the point distribution onto the estimates is studied.

Section 2 introduces the Sequential Quadratic Programming (SQP) as an universal solving approach, which is recommended for nonlinear constraint optimisation problems. Section 3 deals with the least-squares adjustment of a paraboloid. The functional model, the stochastic model, and the objective function are derived for polar observations and Cartesian coordinates, respectively. Based on synthetically generated data, the impact of the coordinate representation is studied in detail by means of Monte-Carlo simulations. Finally, Sect. 4 concludes our investigations.

2 Sequential Quadratic Programming

The Sequential Quadratic Programming (SQP) is a common solving approach in numerical optimisation. The SQP is recommended for optimisation problems with nonlinear constraint functions (Nocedal and Wright, 2006, p. 530f), i. e.,

$$\min \Omega(\mathbf{u}) \quad (1a)$$

subject to

$$f(\mathbf{u}) = \mathbf{0}. \quad (1b)$$

The Lagrangian function $\mathcal{L} = \frac{1}{2}\Omega + \lambda^T f$ is introduced to combine the objective function Ω and the constraint functions f . The unknown parameters \mathbf{u} are estimated iteratively by solving a sequence of quadratic programming subproblems. The optimization problem of the k -th iteration step reads (Lösler, 2021, p. 42)

$$\min \frac{1}{2} \nabla \Omega_k^T \Delta \mathbf{u} + \frac{1}{2} \Delta \mathbf{u}^T \nabla_{\mathbf{u}\mathbf{u}}^2 \mathcal{L}_k \Delta \mathbf{u} \quad (2a)$$

subject to the linear approximation of the constraint functions

$$\mathbf{J}_k \Delta \mathbf{u} + f_k = \mathbf{0}, \quad (2b)$$

where

$$\nabla_{\mathbf{u}\mathbf{u}}^2 \mathcal{L} = \frac{1}{2} \nabla^2 \Omega + \sum_{i=1} \lambda^{(i)} \mathbf{H}^{(i)}$$

denotes the Hessian of the Lagrangian function, and λ are the Lagrange multipliers. Matrices \mathbf{J} and \mathbf{H} are the Jacobian and the Hessian of the constraint functions, respectively. $\nabla \Omega$ and $\nabla^2 \Omega$ denote the gradient and the Hessian of the objective function, respectively. The new iterates $\hat{\mathbf{u}} = \mathbf{u}_k + \Delta \mathbf{u}$ are obtained by solving the quadratic programming subproblem given by Eqs. (2), i. e.,

$$\begin{bmatrix} \nabla_{\mathbf{u}\mathbf{u}}^2 \mathcal{L} & \mathbf{J}^T \\ \mathbf{J} & \mathbf{0} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \Delta \mathbf{u} \\ \hat{\lambda} \end{bmatrix} = - \begin{bmatrix} \frac{1}{2} \nabla \Omega \\ f \end{bmatrix}. \quad (3)$$

As shown by Lösler (2021, p. 45ff) the models frequently used in geodetic sciences, i. e., the model of conditional adjustment, the Gauß-Helmert model, or the Gauß-Markov model, are quadratic programs, which can be interpreted as special cases of the SQP.

3 Best-fit paraboloid

To study the impact of the chosen coordinate representation of the observations onto the estimates, a rotational symmetric paraboloid is adjusted using polar coordinates as well as corresponding Cartesian coordinates.

3.1 Functional model

The functional model describes the relation between the observations space and the parameter space. To keep our investigation as simple as possible, but without losing of generality, we restrict ourselves to the canonical form of a paraboloid given by

$$a \{u_i^2 + v_i^2\} - w_i = 0. \quad (4)$$

The apex and the principal axis of the paraboloid correspond to the origin and the w -axis of the frame, respectively. The Parameter a is a scale parameter that defines the opening of the paraboloid, and the coordinates $(u \ v \ w)_i^T$ refer to an arbitrary position lying on the surface. The commonly used focal length reads

$$F(a) = \frac{1}{4a}. \quad (5)$$

Substituting

$$u_i = x_i - e_{x_i} \quad (6a)$$

$$v_i = y_i - e_{y_i} \quad (6b)$$

$$w_i = z_i - e_{z_i}, \quad (6c)$$

into Eq. (4) yields the constraint function in Eq. (1b) having Cartesian observations $(x \ y \ z)_i^T$ and corresponding residuals $(e_x \ e_y \ e_z)_i^T$. If Cartesian coordinates are used as observations, the vector of unknown parameters reads ¹

$$\mathbf{u}_c^T = [a_c \ \mathbf{e}_c^T] = [a_c \ e_{x_1} \ \dots \ e_{x_i} \ e_{y_i} \ e_{z_i} \ \dots \ e_{z_n}]. \quad (7)$$

Analogously, one found the constraint function in Eq. (1b) having polar observations $(s \ \phi \ \zeta)_i^T$ and corresponding residuals $(e_s \ e_\phi \ e_\zeta)_i^T$ by setting

$$u_i = (s_i - e_{s_i}) \sin(\zeta_i - e_{\zeta_i}) \cos(\phi_i - e_{\phi_i}) \quad (8a)$$

$$v_i = (s_i - e_{s_i}) \sin(\zeta_i - e_{\zeta_i}) \sin(\phi_i - e_{\phi_i}) \quad (8b)$$

$$w_i = (s_i - e_{s_i}) \cos(\zeta_i - e_{\zeta_i}), \quad (8c)$$

where s , ϕ , and ζ are the slope distance, the azimuth angle, and the zenith angle of the i -th position, respectively. If polar observations are used, the vector of unknown parameters reads

¹ A subscript c and p denote the Cartesian and polar observation space, respectively.

$$\mathbf{u}_p^T = [a_p \ \mathbf{e}_p^T] = [a_p \ e_{s_1} \ \dots \ e_{s_i} \ e_{\phi_i} \ e_{\zeta_i} \ \dots \ e_{\zeta_n}]. \quad (9)$$

Obviously, the functional model of Eq. (4) can rigorously be expressed for Cartesian coordinates as well as for polar coordinates.

3.2 Stochastic model

The stochastic model characterises the dispersion of observations by a positive-definite dispersion matrix Σ . If the coordinate representation is changed within the observation space, the stochastic model has to be adapted, using, for instance, the propagation of uncertainty or any other *invertible* method.

Let Σ_p be the dispersion of polar observations, and \mathbf{F} be the coefficient matrix that describes the linearized conversion between polar and Cartesian coordinates, the dispersion of the converted Cartesian observations is obtained by

$$\Sigma_c = \mathbf{F} \Sigma_p \mathbf{F}^T. \quad (10a)$$

Since \mathbf{F}^{-1} exists, the backward conversion reads

$$\Sigma_p = \mathbf{F}^{-1} \Sigma_c (\mathbf{F}^{-1})^T. \quad (10b)$$

Even if Σ is a sparse matrix, for instance, the diagonal variance matrix of the polar observations, i. e.

$$\Sigma_{p,i} = \text{diag} \left(\sigma_s^2 \ \sigma_\phi^2 \ \sigma_\zeta^2 \right)_i, \quad (11a)$$

the converted dispersion matrix of the i -th Cartesian point is usually fully populated, and Σ_c becomes a block diagonal structure,

$$\Sigma_c = \text{blkdiag} (\Sigma_{c,1} \ \dots \ \Sigma_{c,i} \ \dots \ \Sigma_{c,n}). \quad (11b)$$

Having Eqs. (10), a proper method is available to interchange between the dispersion of the coordinate representation of the observations, which is treated as stochastic model.

3.3 Objective function

The objective function is the function that has to be minimised, subjected to the constraint functions. It pro-

vides a global measure of quality of the estimates, because the function increases if the estimates are inadequate. In sense of a least-squares adjustment, the well-known objective function in Eq. (1a) reads

$$\Omega = \mathbf{u}^T \mathbf{W} \mathbf{u} = \mathbf{e}^T \Sigma^{-1} \mathbf{e} \quad (12)$$

where the vector of parameters to be estimated $\mathbf{u}^T = [\mathbf{x}^T \ \mathbf{e}^T]$ is separated into the model parameters \mathbf{x} and the observational residuals \mathbf{e} , Σ is the known positive-definite dispersion matrix of the residuals $\mathbf{e} \sim N(\mathbf{0}, \Sigma)$, and

$$\mathbf{W} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{0} \\ \mathbf{0} & \Sigma^{-1} \end{bmatrix}.$$

Obviously, the SQP does not differ between \mathbf{e} and \mathbf{x} . Both are treated as unknowns within the optimisation, and are explicitly estimated (Lösler and Eschelbach, 2020).

The objective function using polar coordinates reads

$$\Omega_p = \mathbf{e}_p^T \Sigma_p^{-1} \mathbf{e}_p, \quad (13)$$

and the commonly used objective function using Cartesian coordinates is given by

$$\Omega_c = \mathbf{e}_c^T \Sigma_c^{-1} \mathbf{e}_c. \quad (14)$$

As shown by Eqs. (10), the stochastic models are interchangeable. However, equating Eq. (7) with Eq. (9) yields $\mathbf{e}_c = \varepsilon(\bar{\mathbf{e}}_p)$ as the nonlinear function of the polar coordinates (Lösler, 2020), i. e.,

$$e_{x_i} = s_i \sin \zeta_i \cos \phi_i \quad (15a)$$

$$- (s_i - \bar{e}_{s_i}) \sin(\zeta_i - \bar{e}_{\zeta_i}) \cos(\phi_i - \bar{e}_{\phi_i})$$

$$e_{y_i} = s_i \sin \zeta_i \sin \phi_i \quad (15b)$$

$$- (s_i - \bar{e}_{s_i}) \sin(\zeta_i - \bar{e}_{\zeta_i}) \sin(\phi_i - \bar{e}_{\phi_i})$$

$$e_{z_i} = s_i \cos \zeta_i - (s_i - \bar{e}_{s_i}) \cos(\zeta_i - \bar{e}_{\zeta_i}). \quad (15c)$$

Inserting Eq. (15) into Eq. (14) yields the Cartesian objective function rigorously expressed by polar coordinates, i. e.,

$$\bar{\Omega}_p = \varepsilon(\bar{\mathbf{e}}_p)^T \Sigma_c^{-1} \varepsilon(\bar{\mathbf{e}}_p). \quad (16)$$

Figure 1 depicts the condition that must hold for polar residuals and Cartesian residuals, if both representations refer to the identical optimization problem.

Fig. 1 Condition between polar residuals (blue) and Cartesian residuals (red), if both coordinate representations parametrize the identical optimization problem. \mathbf{P} is the observed position and $\hat{\mathbf{P}}$ is the adjusted position, lying on the estimated surface of the paraboloid (green).

Applying the equation of the inverse geodetic problem yields $\mathbf{e}_p = \varepsilon^{-1}(\bar{\mathbf{e}}_c)$ as the nonlinear function of the Cartesian coordinates (Lösler, 2020), i. e.,

$$e_{s_i} = \sqrt{x_i^2 + y_i^2 + z_i^2} \quad (17a)$$

$$- \sqrt{(x_i - \bar{e}_{x_i})^2 + (y_i - \bar{e}_{y_i})^2 + (z_i - \bar{e}_{z_i})^2}$$

$$e_{\phi_i} = \arctan \frac{y_i}{x_i} - \arctan \frac{y_i - \bar{e}_{y_i}}{x_i - \bar{e}_{x_i}} \quad (17b)$$

$$e_{\zeta_i} = \arctan \frac{\sqrt{x_i^2 + y_i^2}}{z_i} \quad (17c)$$

$$- \arctan \frac{\sqrt{(x_i - \bar{e}_{x_i})^2 + (y_i - \bar{e}_{y_i})^2}}{(z_i - \bar{e}_{z_i})}.$$

The polar objective function rigorously expressed by Cartesian coordinates follows from Eqs. (13), (17), i. e.,

$$\bar{\Omega}_c = \varepsilon^{-1}(\bar{\mathbf{e}}_c)^T \Sigma_p^{-1} \varepsilon^{-1}(\bar{\mathbf{e}}_c). \quad (18)$$

In general, the following inequality holds

$$\Omega_p = \bar{\Omega}_c \neq \Omega_c = \bar{\Omega}_p, \quad (19)$$

and the results differ (Lösler and Eschelbach, 2020).

3.4 Example

To demonstrate the impact of the objective function, $n = 60$ points are simulated from Eq. (4), perfectly lying on the surface of the paraboloid. The surface parameter is set to $\tilde{a} = \frac{1}{4}$. The circular distribution of the points is depicted in Fig. 2.

Fig. 2 Topview of the circular distribution of the $n = 60$ simulated points (red dots) lying on the surface of the paraboloid.

Let the measurement instrument be a polar instrument having specified uncertainties $\sigma_s = 5$ mm, $\sigma_\phi = \sigma_\zeta = 5$ mgon, forming the stochastic model via Eq. (11a). The instrument is located in the origin. Such a configuration is already used for surface analyses of VLBI radio telescopes (e.g. Sarti et al., 2009; Bleiders, 2020). The coordinate components of the n points are noised by normally distributed measurement errors $\nabla \sim N(\mathbf{0}, \sigma_0 \mathbf{I})$, where \mathbf{I} is the identity matrix. It should be noted, ∇ cumulates random measurement errors of the instrument but also unknown systematic errors caused by surface deviations (cf. Holst et al., 2015; Lösler et al., 2018).

Polar and Cartesian coordinate components are derived referring to identical point positions. The dispersion of the Cartesian coordinates is obtained by Eq. (10a), and yields a block diagonal matrix, cf. Eq. (11b). Best-fit paraboloids are adjusted treating the $n = 60$ polar and Cartesian coordinates as observations, respectively, as well as the corresponding

stochastic model. Four different objective functions are used given by Eqs. (13), (14), (16), (18).

Table 1 summarizes the obtained results of a single random experiment, which confirm the inequality given by Eq. (19). The estimates are only identical, if the objective functions are referred to the same optimization problem. This condition is fulfilled for $\Omega_p = \bar{\Omega}_c$ and $\Omega_c = \bar{\Omega}_p$ yielding $\hat{F}_p = \hat{F}_c$ and $\hat{F}_c = \hat{F}_p$, respectively.

Table 1 Comparison of estimated focal lengths F using polar and Cartesian coordinates as observations, and four different objective functions. The randomly drawn measurement errors ∇ corresponds to $\sigma_0 = 10$ cm. For demonstration purpose, an increased number of digits is chosen. Results are given in m.

\hat{F}_p	\hat{F}_c	\hat{F}_c	\hat{F}_p
0.998323	0.998323	0.997973	0.997973

Certainly, the reason for the differences in F comes from the used objective functions, which describe different optimization problems. The size of the differences, however, depends on the size of the measurement errors ∇ . To demonstrate these dependencies between $\hat{F}_c - \hat{F}_p$ and the size of the introduced measurement errors $\nabla \sim N(\mathbf{0}, \sigma_0 \mathbf{I})$, a Monte-Carlo simulation is performed using $m = 20000$ samples. Within the simulation, the range of σ_0 is set from 0 cm to 10 cm, using a step size of 1 cm.

Figure 3 depicts the obtained differences $\hat{F}_c - \hat{F}_p$ for various scaled measurement errors ∇ . As expected, the differences increase as the measurement errors get large. However, the maximum difference does not exceed 0.5 % of the measurement error.

Fig. 3 Dependency between $\hat{F}_c - \hat{F}_p$ and the size of the measurement errors $\nabla \sim N(\mathbf{0}, \sigma_0 \mathbf{I})$ for circular distributed surface points.

Nothnagel et al. (2013) study the influence of the distribution of the points on the surface onto the estimates. The authors conclude that a prominent con-

centration of the points near the apex, also shown in Fig. 2, dominates the estimated focal length, and a uniform distribution is recommended (Holst et al., 2015). For that reason, the $n = 60$ points are rearranged in a regular rectangular grid, leading to the configuration depicted in Fig. 4.

Fig. 4 Topview of the rectangular distribution of the $n = 60$ simulated points (red dots) lying on the surface of the paraboloid.

Measurement errors ∇ are added to the points, and polar and rigorous converted Cartesian coordinates are derived referring to identical point positions of the new configuration. Whereas the stochastic model of the polar observations in Eq. (11a) keeps unchanged, the stochastic model of the Cartesian coordinates is derived by Eq. (10a), and yields a block diagonal matrix, cf. Eq. (11b).

Fig. 5 Dependency between $\hat{F}_c - \hat{F}_p$ and the size of the measurement errors $\nabla \sim N(\mathbf{0}, \sigma_0 \mathbf{I})$ for rectangular distributed surface points.

Figure 5 depicts the dependencies between $\hat{F}_c - \hat{F}_p$ and the measurement errors $\nabla \sim N(\mathbf{0}, \sigma_0 \mathbf{I})$, obtained by a Monte-Carlo simulation, using $m = 20000$ samples. The range of σ_0 is set from 0 cm to 10 cm, using a step size of 1 cm. The curve indicates a similar behavior as already shown in Fig. 3. If the measurement errors get large, the differences also increase. Identical results are obtained if and only if $\nabla = \mathbf{0}$.

The chosen distribution of the observed positions on the surface has only a marginal effect onto the estimates. Even for $\sigma_0 = 10$ cm, the differences between the estimated focal lengths are < 1 mm, as summarized in Table 2. The differences between the estimated focal lengths and the true value $F(\bar{a}) = 1$ m result from the nonlinearity of the functional model (Lösler et al., 2020). The smallest bias is obtained for the rectangular distributed surface points and \hat{F}_p , and confirms the recommendation given by Holst et al. (2015).

Table 2 Estimated focal lengths \hat{F} for circular and rectangular distributed surface points, respectively. Estimates are derived from polar observations as well as Cartesian coordinates, using Monte-Carlo simulations and varying measurement errors, indicated by σ_0 . Focal lengths \hat{F} are given in m, σ_0 is given in cm.

σ_0	Circular		Rectangular	
	\hat{F}_c	\hat{F}_p	\hat{F}_c	\hat{F}_p
0	1.0000	1.0000	1.0000	1.0000
1	1.0000	1.0000	1.0000	1.0000
2	0.9999	0.9999	0.9999	1.0000
3	0.9999	0.9999	0.9999	1.0000
4	0.9997	0.9998	0.9998	0.9999
5	0.9996	0.9997	0.9997	0.9998
6	0.9993	0.9995	0.9996	0.9998
7	0.9992	0.9994	0.9994	0.9997
8	0.9990	0.9993	0.9993	0.9996
9	0.9987	0.9991	0.9991	0.9996
10	0.9985	0.9989	0.9988	0.9994

The recommendation for the surface accuracy of a VGOS radio telescope is specified by < 0.2 mm (Petrauchenko et al., 2009, p. 24), and, thus, fifty-times smaller than the maximum simulated errors. The differences between the chosen objective functions, and the differences between the point distributions under consideration are on the same order of magnitude. If both, the deviations of the surface and the measurement uncertainties of the instrument, are small, all approaches yield comparable results.

4 Conclusion

The parameters of synthetically generated paraboloids were adjusted, using different coordinate representations. For this purpose, the functional model, the stochastic model, and the objective function were derived for polar observations and for rigorous converted Cartesian coordinates, respectively. The impact of the coordinate representation of the observation space onto the parameters to be estimated was studied in detail.

Using Sequential Quadratic Programming, it has been shown that the proper transformation of the functional and the stochastic model is not sufficient to obtain identical results, because also an adapted objective function is required to get corresponding estimates. Moreover, the impact of the point distribution onto the estimates was investigated by means of Monte-Carlo simulations. The focal lengths, obtained by a circular distribution, were compared to the focal lengths, derived by a rectangular distribution. Both, the realized configuration and the chosen objective function affect the parameters to be estimated. However, if the residuals are quite small, these differences are usually negligible.

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